

ALKYLATION REACTIONS OF ISOCYANATES**Khatamova Mukhabbat Sattarovna**

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Annotation: In this article, the course of the reaction and the influence of the isomer composition on the radical nature, branching and length of the molecule, solvent, and the “hardness” or “softness” of the methylating agent were studied by determining the reactivity of the N-H alkylation of carbamate and bis-carbamate derivatives with alkyl halides.

Keywords: carbamate, bis-carbamate, isocyanate, carbon-nitrogen bond, N,N'-disodium derivative, methyl iodide, benzene.

Introduction

Currently, carbamate and bis-carbamate derivatives are widely used in the chemical industry, catalysts, agrochemistry, medicine, pharmaceuticals and various other fields, and are of great importance as pharmacologically active substances in many drugs, in particular as sedatives, analgesics and antipsychotics, in agrochemistry, in agriculture, in pest control, in the chemical industry, in the production of plastics and other materials, in the food industry, in improving the quality of products and preserving products. This is one of the urgent tasks facing chemistry to meet the needs of the national economy in bioactive substances and to search for new compounds, develop technologies for their production and apply them in practice.

Carbamates and their derivatives are highly reactive synthons in the field of basic organic synthesis of biologically active compounds.

Level of study

A number of patents, articles and monographs have been published on the chemistry of carbamates and their chemical properties. Also, scientists who have contributed and are contributing to the study of the subject: S.G. Entelis, O.B. Nesterov, H.H. Melnikov, Henkel Kгаа, Heinzce Michael, S.Yu. Vyazmin, S.E. Berezina, L.A. Remizova, I.N. Domnin, R. Glyater, Mitsui Chemicals, Aso Shinji, Noguchi Takeshi, Ogawa Shinji and other specialists from the CIS, European, German and American countries have also contributed.

Among the scientists from Uzbekistan: A.G. Maksumov, N. Madikhanov, U.A. Baltaboyev, M.A. Atakhodzhayeva, N.A. Avinov, U. Tadjibayev, M.A. Talipova, A.D. Zakirov, U.B. Ju'rayev, U.A. Aripov, O.V. Afanasyeva, H.U. Usmanov, Z.G. Khaydarova, B.S. Sulaymanov, M.S. Khatamova and others are conducting scientific research in this area.

Research methods

Mono- and diisocyanates are highly reactive substances, and a wide variety of their compounds are known, which are of great interest both theoretically and practically. Using these methods, the authors used to obtain a number of isocyanates in high yields. The importance of isocyanates can be further enhanced by obtaining urea derivatives, which are products of the reaction of isocyanates with alcohols. When studying the chemical properties of isocyanates, it is necessary to dwell on the structure of the $-N=C=O-$ groups and the distribution of electron clouds in isocyanate molecules in both static and dynamic states, since it is these factors that often determine the nature of the reactions in which isocyanates enter.

Isocyanate groups are a linearly arranged (cumulative) system in which π -orbitals can be divided into two orthogonal systems π_x and π_y - orbitals. Due to the energy splitting of orbitals, the interaction of electrons in this orbital with electrons in the π -system is significantly greater than that of localized σ -component electrons. The presence of such π, π -bonding indicates that the $-N=C$ bond in the $O=C=N-R-N=C=O$ and $-N=C=O$ molecules has a reduced length. Therefore, a model is used in isocyanates that treats the orbital as a π -orbital (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of electron clouds in the isocyanate molecule

The reactivity of the NCO group is determined by its electronic structure. Some information on the electronic structure of the NCO group was obtained from [1,2], and the results of the calculation of the distribution of the π -electron density in methyl and phenyl isocyanates were performed using the coordinated field method in the Pariser-Parra-Poplo approximation. Often, the carbon atoms in the

NCO group have a large positive charge, which determines the ability of isocyanates to bind nucleophilic reagents:

Calculations show that the reaction proceeds through a large weakening of the $-\text{N}=\text{C}<$ bond compared to the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ bond. The change in the electron configuration is higher in the $-\text{N}=\text{C}<$ bond than in the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ bond. When the reacting particles approach, the negative charge on the nitrogen atom increases significantly compared to the oxygen atom in the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group. This factor indicates that the polarizability of the $-\text{N}=\text{C}$ bond is greater than that of the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ bond and it is precisely the $-\text{N}=\text{C}<$ bond that should be easily broken when the $-\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{O}$ group is attacked by nucleophilic reagents.

The carbon-nitrogen bond of the isocyanate group, due to the mobility of the active hydrogen atom, enters into ionic addition reactions with functional compounds such as water, alcohols, phenols, thiols, amines, amides, and carboxylic acids.

Isocyanates undergo alkylation reactions to form three main cyclic compounds: amides and ureas.

Without the presence of a catalyst, these reactions usually occur with isocyanates and are coupled. It is assumed that they proceed with the formation of an intermediate complex containing the compound. According to this mechanism, the compound added to the intermediate complex is attached to the second molecule. Therefore, the reaction is a first-order, active reaction with respect to the isocyanate.

Alkylation of the N-N group in carbamates with alkyl halides is of great interest for determining the reactivity of compounds containing N-H.

Alkylation reactions can be carried out by reacting the N,N'-disodium derivatives of hexamethylene bis-[(alkyl)-carbamates] with methyl iodide in

benzene at room temperature at 25-260°C. The fact that alkylation reactions proceed at the nitrogen atom in N,N is explained by the relatively easy dissociation of the sodium atom due to the presence of a carbonyl group next to this atom.

Studies of the methylation reactions of N,N'-disodium hexamethylene bis-[(alkyl)-carbamates] show that the course of the reaction and the isomer composition depend on the nature of the radical, the branching and length of the molecule, the solvent, the "hard" or "soft" nature of the methylating agent, and other factors.

The alkylation of the above compounds with alkyl halides CH₃X is of undoubted interest in determining the nature and degree of substitution of the methylating agent in the halide "X" in the reagent. The physical properties of CH₃X are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Physical properties of CH₃X

Halogen compounds	Boiling temperature, °C				d ₄ ²⁰			
	F	Cl	Br	I	F	Cl	Br	I
CH ₃ X	-79	-24	4	42	--	0,991 (25°C)	1,732 (0°C)	2,279

Alkanes are chlorinated under the influence of UV light or temperature. An equimolar mixture of methane and chlorine can explode. Therefore, the chlorination reaction is carried out in a reactor with a UV lamp, with an excess of alkane. The reaction proceeds stepwise according to the free radical mechanism.

Hydrogen on the tertiary carbon atom exchanges more easily, hydrogen on the secondary carbon atom more difficult. Halogenated methyls belonging to primary compounds of normal structure can be easily identified by considering their boiling points and relative densities. In CH₃J, the relative densities and boiling points are higher than those of the corresponding bromine-substituted ones, and in turn, the densities and boiling points of bromine-substituted ones are higher than those of chlorine-substituted ones.

In conclusion, the relative density of CH₃X increases with increasing atomic weight of X in the molecule. In addition, it also depends on the bond energy, size, etc. (Table 2).

Table 2

General properties of bonds in C-X

Connect ion	Energy, kkal/mol	Length, A ⁰	Polarity, D	Polarizability, cm ³
C-F	102	1,40	2,3	1,7
C-Cl	78	1,76	2,3	6,5
C-Br	65	1,91	2,2	9,6
C-I	57	2,12	2,0	14,6

Organic molecules are characterized by polarizability, that is, the ability to increase the polarity of the bond when an attacking agent approaches. The more mobile the electron cloud of the atoms forming the bond, the higher the polarizability of the bond. The tendency to polarizability is best observed in the series of C-X bonds.

Electron-withdrawing substituents increase the reactivity of isocyanates, which occurs in the reaction with nucleophilic compounds, regardless of whether the increase in positive charge on the carbon atom is calculated or due to the stabilization of the transition state, while electron-donating substituents reduce it.

Thus, the closer the polarity of the CH₃-F, CH₃-Cl, CH₃-Br and CH₃I bonds, the greater the polarizability of the C-I bond compared to that of the C-F. In all nucleophilic substitution (S_N) reactions, C-I is maximally active relative to other C-X, in strict accordance with the polarizability.

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